

Brain imaging and registration in larval zebrafish

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Abstract

Registration of larval zebrafish brain scans to a common reference brain enables comparison of transgene and gene expression patterns, neuroanatomy, and morphometry. Here we describe step-by-step methods for staining and mounting larval zebrafish to facilitate whole-brain fluorescence imaging of transgenic lines, immunohistochemical and dye stains and mRNA localization using hybridization chain reaction. Following image acquisition, we provide a template for aligning brain images to a reference atlas using non-linear registration with the ANTs software package.

Introduction

Three-dimensional image registration is widely used in human brain imaging studies so that samples can easily be compared or subjected to quantitative statistical analysis. Recently, brain registration methods have also been used in zebrafish, where the entire larval brain can be imaged at cellular resolution using standard confocal or light-sheet microscopy. Following acquisition, images may be registered to a digital brain atlas, allowing samples to be automatically annotated with neuroanatomical information, compared to results from previous experiments, or used for morphometric studies. Brain registration accuracy in zebrafish is primarily limited by intrinsic biological variability, resulting in alignment errors that are approximately the diameter of a single neuron (1). Registration algorithms require one or more reference brain images generated from fluorescent markers that are present in the target brain atlas. Suitable references include transgenic lines with broad expression of a fluorescent protein (e.g. *vGlut:dsRed*), immunohistochemical stains against common proteins (e.g. tERK), or fluorescent dyes (e.g. LysoTracker). Images acquired from either live or fixed samples may be used; in fact, when fixed samples are registered to a live brain reference, distortions introduced by fixation may be corrected by local elastic alignment (1). Several open-source packages have been successfully used to align zebrafish brain images to a reference, including CMTK (2,3), minctracc (4) and Advanced Normalization Tools (ANTs) (1,5). These algorithms each first apply linear transformations (such as rotation and scaling) to loosely align images to the reference brain, then achieve a precise match through local non-linear deformations. Here we describe a protocol for whole-brain imaging of larval zebrafish brains, followed by computational registration to a brain atlas using Advanced Normalization Tools (ANTs).

Materials

Sample files and other resources referenced below may be downloaded from the Zenodo Registration Utility archive (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5847085>).

Reagents and equipment for mounting and imaging embryos

- E3 embryo medium (5 mM NaCl, 0.17 mM KCl, 0.33 mM CaCl₂, 0.33 mM MgSO₄ in ddH₂O)
- N-Phenylthiourea (PTU; Sigma, Catalog #222909), prepared as 300 μM solution in E3 embryo medium

- Tricaine methanesulfonate (Sigma, Catalog #E10521). Stock solution prepared as 0.2% solution in 1L MilliQ H₂O, pH 7.2
- Low melting temperature agarose: NuSieve™ GTG™ Agarose (Lonza, Catalog #50080), prepared as 2.5% solution in H₂O
- Thermo Scientific Lab-Tek II Chambered Coverglass, 2-well (Fisher, Catalog #12565336)
- 3D printed chambered coverglass insert (Zenodo Registration Utility archive: **mounting_insert.stl**)
- Laser scanning confocal microscope with 488, 561, and 633 laser lines, 20x or 25x water objective, and software with tile scanning ability.
- Fiji (i.e. ImageJ) software (<https://fiji.sc/>) for image processing. To load and save images in the NIfTI format, download and install the NIfTI Input/Output plugin from <https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/plugins/nifti.html>
- If staining brains for live imaging, LysoTracker™ Deep Red (Invitrogen, Catalog #L12492)

Brain registration

- Hardware requirements. ANTs requires around 12 Gb of memory to register a 2x2x2 μm resolution image. For 1 μm isotropic resolution, around 80 Gb memory is needed.
- Download and install ANTs (<http://stnava.github.io/ANTs/>). ANTs can be run on several operating systems. For a linux system, we recommend installing ANTs using the script **installANTs.sh**, which can be downloaded from <https://github.com/cookpa/antsInstallExample>. You will need *cmake* and *git* already installed on your system.
- Reference brain image. Several reference brains are available in the Zenodo Reference Brain archive: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3367708>
- Digital brain atlas file (Zenodo Registration Utility archive: **zbb-region-atlas.nii.gz**) for brain region annotation.

Stepwise methods

Select a registration channel

1. Select a transgene, dye, or antibody stain that will be used to drive the brain registration, based on your experimental design and the spectral lines that are available on your microscope. Recommended registration channels are described below and summarized in Table 1. Live imaging is preferred where

possible, as tissue fixation distorts brain structure, although these changes can be partially corrected by the brain registration procedure.

2. For imaging the expression pattern in a transgenic line, cross the line to *vGlut2a: DsRed* (*TgBAC(slc17a6b[vglut2a]:loxP-DsRed-loxP-GFP)nns14* (6)), *vGlut2a:GFP* (converted from *vGlut2a: DsRed* by Cre mRNA injection), or *tuba:mCardinal* (*Tg(Cau.Tuba1a:MCardinal)y516* (7)), available from the Zebrafish International Resource Center, <http://zebrafish.org>), as these expression patterns can be directly aligned to the **vglut-ref-01** and **tuba-mcar-ref-01** reference brain images, respectively. Whole-brain GCaMP experiments can be registered to the **huc-gcamp5g-ref-01** reference brain using the GCaMP expression pattern.

3. If transgenic lines are not available or are inconvenient (for example, when performing morphometric analysis of brain structure in mutant animals), live imaging can be performed using LysoTracker vital dye staining (Section 3.3) and registered using the **lyso-ref-01** reference brain image. Morphometry can also be achieved by labeling brain tissue with antibody staining (8).

4. For immunohistochemical markers, co-staining with antibody labeling against MAP Kinase (tERK) is recommended for registration to the **terk-ref-01** reference image.

5. For visualizing RNA expression using hybridization chain reaction (HCR) *in situ* labeling, we recommend performing the experiment in transgenic *vGlut2a:GFP* expressing embryos, as GFP fluorescence survives the procedure and can be aligned to the **vglut-ref-01** reference brain image. Alternatively, if this is not possible, we recommend simultaneously using a second HCR probe set against *elavl3*, which is commonly used in HCR protocols as a positive control. The **HCR-huc-ref-01** reference image should be used for registration with *elavl3* HCR staining.

Raise larvae

1. Raise embryos at 28°C in 300 µM PTU dissolved in E3 embryo medium until 6 days post fertilization (dpf).

2. If imaging transgenes, sort larvae for transgene expression. Larvae are easiest to sort before the swim bladder inflates at 4 dpf. *vglut2a:GFP/DsRed* and *tuba:mCardinal* transgenes begin expressing by 1 dpf and can be conveniently sorted at this stage.

Label brain tissue with a fluorescent marker

1. For tERK antibody labeling or *elavl3* HCR refer to published protocols (9,10).

2. For LysoTracker staining (11) follow steps 3-4.

3. At 5 dpf, transfer larvae raised in 300 μ M PTU to 300 μ M PTU containing 1% DMSO and 1 μ M LysoTracker.
4. Incubate 12-16 hours at 28°C in dim light, then transfer from LysoTracker solution to fresh PTU just prior to imaging.

Mount larvae for imaging

The steps below describe mounting larvae for imaging using an inverted confocal microscope. Larvae can also be imaged using an upright microscope. For imaging using an upright microscope, larvae need to be mounted dorsal side up. Dorsal mounting can be facilitated using a specialized mold (12), or by mounting ventral side up (as described below), then removing the block of agarose containing the larva from the mounting insert, flipping it over, and replacing it in the mounting insert.

1. Boil low melt agarose and cool to 55°C in an incubator or water bath.
2. Place 3D printed chamber inserts into coverglass chambers.
3. Anesthetize larvae in 10 ml of E3 with 0.5 ml Tricaine stock solution.
4. Draw a larva into the tip of a glass Pasteur pipet with \sim 5 μ L E3.
5. Fill a well of the chamber insert with 2.5% low melt agarose.
6. Pipet the larva into the agarose (Fig. 1A).
7. Immediately push the larva to the bottom of the chamber by applying gentle pressure at the swim bladder with a pipet tip or forceps tips. The larva should be oriented ventral side up with the head to the left. The dorsal surface of the head should be flush against the coverslip with the tail sticking up (Fig. 1B). Hold the larva down until the agarose starts to set, making sure that the larva does not float up from the coverslip.
8. Mount remaining larvae in other chambers and cover with a few drops of E3 with tricaine.

Confocal imaging

Any conventional confocal microscope can be used for imaging. To achieve the required resolution for registration, a 20x or 25x objective with a high numerical aperture (\sim 0.95 or higher) and a working distance of at least 350 μ m should be used. In most cases, tile scanning will be required to image the

entirety of the brain from the olfactory epithelia in the forebrain to the caudal-most region of the hindbrain (see Fig. 2). The caudal boundary of the hindbrain aligns with the end of the third myomere but otherwise does not have a salient morphological feature (13).

1. Set up tile scanning so that the entire brain will be included in the image once tiled.
2. Set voxel size to 1x1x1 or 2x2x2 μm depending on the resolution needed for your experiment. We suggest using 1 μm resolution for imaging transgene expression patterns, tERK staining, HCR and reconstructing neuronal projections. Brain morphometry may be performed at 2 μm resolution, as in any case, images will likely be smoothed and downsampled to facilitate downstream computation. If using 2 μm resolution images, then it will be most efficient to register images to the 2 μm resolution reference brains in the Zenodo Reference Brain archive, which have the 'R2' designation in the filename.
3. Make sure no image processing features are set that can affect pixel intensity or noise filtering during the acquisition.
4. Set up z-stack from the dorsal surface of the brain to the ventral hypothalamus (Fig. 3). Set step size to 1 or 2 μm resolution.
5. Display saturated pixels. Set up z-compensation by scanning every 50 μm and adjusting laser power so that the brightest pixels in the image have reached saturation. You will likely have to increase the laser power for all channels as you image more ventrally.
6. Acquire image stacks for all larvae.

Post-imaging processing

1. If image stacks were acquired using tiling, stitch tiles together into a single image stack comprising the entire brain, using either Fiji or software included with the microscope.
2. Use ImageJ to rotate image stacks so that they are oriented in the same direction as the reference image. For the sample images here, they should be rotated so that the anterior end of the head faces left. Similarly, ensure that the image stacks have the same dorso-ventral direction as the reference.
3. The image dimension units (i.e., the units of pixel length/width and depth) of your stacks should match those of the reference brain. Typically, this will be in either mm or μm . Set image dimension units to microns in Fiji by entering the word 'micron' in the image property 'Unit of length' field.
4. If using multiple fluorophores, split stacks into separate channels using Fiji. If using simultaneous acquisition for multiple channels, you may need to perform spectral unmixing to eliminate bleed through. This can be done using confocal-specific software or Fiji.

5. Save stacks as 16 bit NIfTI files. Although these are 16 bit files, do not include intensity values greater than 32767 as this will result in negative pixel values in the output image. If necessary, use Fiji to rescale intensity values to remain below this limit. The sample files are gzipped NIfTI files (.nii.gz); however, compressing input files is not essential.

6. Following processing, images should match the reference brain dimension units and orientation. For processing large numbers of images, a sample Fiji macro (**stitch-3channel-image-stacks.ijm**) that performs all of these steps is available in the Zenodo Registration Utility archive.

Brain registration

Two ANTs programs are run to generate a brain image that is registered to the reference brain: *antsRegistration* and *antsApplyTransforms*. *antsRegistration* computes and saves a transformation matrix by comparing the brain image to the reference brain. *antsApplyTransforms* applies the transformation matrix to the brain image and saves a registered image. The sample files referenced below can be downloaded from the Zenodo Registration Utility archive and used to troubleshoot the image registration process. The sample reference brain image (**reference.nii.gz**) is the **vglut-ref-R2-01** reference brain. In the brain that will be registered to this reference, channel 1 (**brain1-01.nii.gz**) is DsRed fluorescence from the *vglut2a:DsRed* transgene, and channel 2 (**brain1-02.nii.gz**) is Kaede fluorescence from *Et(SCP1:GAL4FF)y265, Tg(UAS-E1b:Kaede)s1999t* (14).

1. Save the reference brain file (**reference.nii.gz**), and the brain image files to the same folder. If the brain image (**brain1**) has multiple fluorescence channels, then name the file that has the same fluorescence marker as the reference **brain1-01.nii.gz**, and name the other channel **brain1-02.nii.gz**.

2. Run the *antsRegistration* command. Before running, you may limit the number of threads that ANTs uses with the command `export ITK_GLOBAL_DEFAULT_NUMBER_OF_THREADS=8` (or other suitable value). This is especially important on a cluster or shared system to avoid overusing resources. Adapt the command from Step 1 in Table 2 substituting filenames as needed. Images acquired from fixed brain tissue typically require greater deformation to achieve a close match than is needed for live brain scans. The major difference between the live and fixed parameter sets is that the fixed parameter set allows greater local elastic registration. While this is useful for correcting fixation artifacts, it can also introduce potentially severe local distortions into the sample image, for example, causing axon tracts to appear bent, or cell bodies to elongate. Therefore, depending on the samples, select either the live (Step 1a) or the fixed tissue (Step 1b) command from Table 2. In some cases you may have acquired multiple fluorescence channels that are also present in the target image. Multiple channels can be used simultaneously during registration to improve accuracy.

3. For a 2 μm isotropic resolution image, *antsRegistration* may take 1-2 hours to run (using 12 threads, on Intel Xeon 6140 processors), and on completion will output three transformation matrices. If using the sample files, these will be designated **brain1_0GenericAffine.mat**, **brain1_1Warp.nii.gz** and

brain1_1InverseWarp.nii.gz

4. Run the *antsApplyTransforms* command (adapt Step 2a in Table 2) to apply the transformation matrix to the first channel. This command should typically take around 1 min to complete and will save the registered brain image as **brain1-01_registered.nii**. After registration, the image (in this case **brain1-01_registered.nii**) should have the same width, height and depth (in pixels) as the reference brain. However, it will be a 32-bit image and the dimensions will be specified in millimeters instead of microns.
5. If your brain image has multiple fluorescent channels, you may also run the *antsApplyTransforms* command to apply the same transformation matrix to additional channels (Step 2b in Table 2). The registered second channel will be saved as **brain1-02_registered.nii**. If you have more than 2 channels, modify the command in Step 2b accordingly (change brain1-02 to brain1-03, brain1-04, etc.).
6. The registered brain images can now be compared with a digital brain atlas file, for example, by loading both files into Fiji and synchronously scrolling through to check annotations, or by loading the registered file into the Zebrafish Brain Browser. To load stacks into the web-based version of the Zebrafish Brain Browser (ZBB), stacks should be converted to 2D montage files, as described at <http://vis.arc.vt.edu/projects/zbb/help/>. NIfTI files can be directly loaded into the desktop version of ZBB.
7. To measure the size of brain regions in the original images, it may be useful to inverse-transform an atlas file back onto the original brain scans. To do so, run the *antsApplyTransforms* command with the inverse transformation matrix (Step 3a in Table 2). When complete, the inverse-transformed atlas will be saved in your folder as **brain1_regions.nii.gz**. You may then estimate the size of a brain region by summing the number of voxels labeled with the matching index. After transforming the ZBB atlas back onto the original brain scans, the output file should have the same dimensions (in x,y,z) as the scan. The boundaries of the inverse-transformed atlas should closely match the contour of the brain in the image stack. Alternatively, you may inverse-transform an atlas with larger brain divisions (e.g. Pallium, Cerebellum) annotated (Step 3b in Table 2 ; the larger brain divisions in **zbb-division-atlas.nii.gz** are agglomerations of the small computationally derived regions in the **zbb-region-atlas.nii.gz** file).
8. When comparing wildtype and mutant brain structure, it may be instructive to examine which parts of the brain were locally dilated or contracted to fit the reference brain. To create an image stack that contains this information, run the command in Step 4 of Table 2. This will produce a new file called **brain1_jac.nii.gz** in which the value of each pixel indicates if the pixel in the original image was expanded or contracted to match the reference. With these parameters, this command calculates the log of the Jacobian determinant of the image. The output file has the same dimensions as the reference brain: pixels were inflated to match the reference brain have positive values, and pixels that were compressed to match the reference have negative values.
9. Brain scans may be used to reconstruct neuronal projections. To register a set of x,y,z coordinates that describe a neuron's morphology into the coordinate system of the reference brain, first save a comma separated text file **brain1-01.csv** in the directory above. The first line (header) of this file should be "x,y,z,t,label,comment". The first three columns are the x,y,z coordinates (in millimeters, not microns); t

is 0 ; label is the point number ; comment is the point to which it connects. A sample file is available in the Zenodo Registration Utility archive. A python script that converts standard swc format files to csv files is available the same archive (**swc-to-ants.py**). Finally, run the *antsApplyTransformsToPoints* command (Step 5 in Table 2). The dimension units in the output file will be in mm, even if all the input files and reference are in microns.

10. After registration, brain images may be compared to determine if genes or transgenes express in similarly located cells. Due to registration errors and biological variability, essential conclusions about co-localization should be empirically confirmed using multiple probes in the same sample.

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Table 1: Suggested fluorescent labels and matching reference brains for common experimental conditions. ^a Reference brains where a downsampled 2 x 2 x 2 μm reference brain is also available in the Zenodo Reference Brain archive (indicated by 'R2' in the cognate filename). ^b Various *elavl3:GCaMP* lines are available and have sufficiently similar patterns to match the suggested reference brain.

Experimental condition	Fluorescent label in sample	Reference brain for registration
Live imaging green fluorescence	<i>Tg(vGlut2a:DsRed)nns14</i>	vglut-ref-01.nii.gz ^a
Live imaging green fluorescence	<i>Tg(tuba:mCardinal)y516</i>	tuba-mcar-ref-01.nii.gz ^a
Live imaging red fluorescence	<i>Tg(vGlut2a:GFP)nns14</i>	vglut-ref-01.nii.gz ^a
Whole-brain calcium imaging	<i>Tg(elavl3:GCaMP)</i> ^b	huc-gcamp5g-ref-01.nii.gz
Structural brain imaging	LysoTracker vital dye	lyso-ref-01.nii.gz ^a
Immunofluorescence	anti-tERK	terk-ants-ref-02.nii.gz
Hybridization chain reaction in situ	<i>Tg(vGlut2a:GFP)nns14</i>	vglut-ref-01.nii.gz ^a
Hybridization chain reaction in situ	HCR using <i>elavl3</i> probe	HCR-huc-ref-01.nii.gz

Table 2: ANTs commands for brain registration using sample images provided in the Zenodo Registration Utility archive.

Step	Purpose	Command
1a	Produce matrix that transforms brain scan from live brain scan to reference image	antsRegistration -d 3 --float 1 -o [brain1_] --interpolation WelchWindowedSinc --use-histogram-matching 0 -r [reference.nii.gz,brain1-01.nii.gz,1] -t rigid[0.1] -m MI[reference.nii.gz,brain1-01.nii.gz,1,32,Regular,0.25] -c [200x200x200x0,1e-8,10] --shrink-factors 12x8x4x2 --smoothing-sigmas 4x3x2x1vox -t Affine[0.1] -m MI[reference.nii.gz,brain1-01.nii.gz,1,32,Regular,0.25] -c [200x200x200x0,1e-8,10] --shrink-factors 12x8x4x2 --smoothing-sigmas 4x3x2x1vox -t SyN[0.05,6,0.5] -m CC[reference.nii.gz,brain1-01.nii.gz,1,2] -c [200x200x200x200x10,1e-7,10] --shrink-factors 12x8x4x2x1 --smoothing-sigmas 4x3x2x1x0vox
1b	Produce matrix that transforms brain scan from fixed tissue brain scan to reference image	antsRegistration -d 3 --float 1 -o [brain1_] --interpolation WelchWindowedSinc --use-histogram-matching 0 -r [reference.nii.gz,brain1-01.nii.gz,1] -t rigid[0.1] -m MI[reference.nii.gz,brain1-01.nii.gz,1,32,Regular,0.25] -c [200x200x200x0,1e-8,10] --shrink-factors 12x8x4x2 --smoothing-sigmas 4x3x2x1vox -t Affine[0.1] -m MI[reference.nii.gz,brain1-01.nii.gz,1,32,Regular,0.25] -c [200x200x200x0,1e-8,10] --shrink-factors 12x8x4x2 --smoothing-sigmas 4x3x2x1vox -t SyN[0.1,6,0] -m CC[reference.nii.gz,brain1-01.nii.gz,1,2] -c [200x200x200x200x10,1e-7,10] --shrink-factors 12x8x4x2x1 --smoothing-sigmas 4x3x2x1x0vox
2a	Produce registered brain image for first channel	antsApplyTransforms -d 3 -v 0 --float -n WelchWindowedSinc -i brain1-01.nii.gz -r reference.nii.gz -o brain1-01_registered.nii.gz -t brain1_1Warp.nii.gz -t brain1_0GenericAffine.mat
2b	Produce registered brain image for second channel	antsApplyTransforms -d 3 -v 0 --float -n WelchWindowedSinc -i brain1-02.nii.gz -r reference.nii.gz -o brain1-02_registered.nii.gz -t brain1_1Warp.nii.gz -t brain1_0GenericAffine.mat
3a	Annotate original brain scan with atlas of brain regions	antsApplyTransforms -d 3 -v 0 --float -n MultiLabel -i zbb-region-atlas.nii.gz -r brain1-01.nii.gz -o brain1_regions.nii.gz -t [brain1_0GenericAffine.mat,1] -t brain1_1InverseWarp.nii.gz
3b	Annotate original brain scan with atlas of brain divisions	antsApplyTransforms -d 3 -v 0 --float -n MultiLabel -i zbb-division-atlas.nii.gz -r brain1-01.nii.gz -o brain1_divisions.nii.gz -t [brain1_0GenericAffine.mat,1] -t brain1_1InverseWarp.nii.gz
4	Visualize the transformation matrix	CreateJacobianDeterminantImage 3 brain1_1InverseWarp.nii.gz brain1_jac.nii.gz 1
5	Register neuron trace to reference image	antsApplyTransformsToPoints -d 3 -i brain1-neuron1.csv -o brain1-neuron1_registered_points.csv -t [brain1_0GenericAffine.mat,1] -t brain1_1InverseWarp.nii.gz

Figures

Figure 1: Mounting larval zebrafish for confocal imaging

- A. Schematic of mounting 6 dpf zebrafish using 3D printed chamber insert
- B. Orientation of a well-mounted zebrafish larva with dorsal surface of the head in contact with coverslip (blue) for imaging on an inverted confocal microscope

Figure 2: Sample whole-brain image

Single slice image of *vGlut2a:DsRed* reference brain (grey) showing olfactory epithelia (OE) at anterior boundary and posterior hindbrain boundary between myomeres 3 and 4 (visualized using *bActin:GFP*). Image stacks should comprise the area between the dotted lines.

Figure 3: Imaging depth required to resolve ventral brain structures

A-E. Examples of single slices through confocal images of 6 dpf brains using fluorescent labels in Table 1, showing desirable image quality 280 μm from dorsal surface. F. Schematic indicating depth of slices shown (dotted line). H, Hypothalamus; oc, optic chiasm ; OV, otic vesicle ; R, retina; SAG, statoacoustic ganglion; Tg, Trigeminal ganglion. Arrow indicates anterior.